

ANNEX 6. Catalogue of weather and climate insurance solutions

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#ID	Link to source	Name of solution (if any)	Innovation type	Insurance solution pillar and reference number*	LOB**	Status***
001	LINK	Trockenheitsversicherung, Ernteschutz Vario	Data use	P&P #1a	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
002	LINK	CYA XLab	Data use	P&P #3a	Agro	TRL7 (deployment)
003	LINK	Low Temperature insurance	Data use	P&P #3a	Agro	TRL2 (research)
004	NA, personal communication	Meteorological data index product for olive- or grape-diseases.	Data use	P&P #1a, #3a, DTM #1a, #1b, #1c, #2	Agro	TRL2 (research)
005	LINK	Temperature index product covering apple quality for spring frost.	Data use	P&P #1a, #3a	Agro	TRL1 (research)
006	LINK	Temperature - humidity index predicting dairy cow milk yield and protein content due to heat-humidity stress.	Data use	P&P #3a	Agro	TRL1 (research)
007	LINK	Farm-specific combination of different drought indices.	Data use	P&P #3a	Agro	TRL1 (research)
008	LINK 1 LINK 2	Parametric forestry wildfire cover	Data use	P&P #1a	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
009	LINK	Risk and damage assessment data base	Data use	DTM #1, #4	Agro	TRL2 (research)
010	LINK	Municipal Flood Management through Effective Knowledge Curation	Data use	SH #1a	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)

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011	LINK	Opti-crop Index tracker	Data use	DTM #4	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
012	LINK	Soil Moisture Deficit Index Insurance	Data use	P&P #1a, DTM #1b	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
013	LINK	NatCatService	Data use	BM #2a, SH #1	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
014	LINK	Connectivity Hub	Data use	DTM #4	House/ Building	TRL4 (development)
015	LINK	CyStellar Terra-Risk Re	Data use	DTM #1b, #4	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
016	LINK	Sharing of loss data	Data use	SH #1	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
017	LINK	Two-year national initiative	Data use	DTM #1	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
018	LINK	Sustainability Bond	Financial	SH #2e, BM #4b	Infra-structure	TRL9 (deployment)
019	LINK	Green bond issuing	Financial	SH #2e	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
020	LINK	Smart reinsurance contracts	Financial	DTM #2 (new IT), SH #2d	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
021	LINK 1 LINK 2	Resilience Bond Insurance	Financial	BM #4b	Non-LoB specific	TRL5 (development)
022	LINK	Prospective Structured Reinsurance	Financial	SH #2d	Non-LoB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
023	LINK	DLT-based cat swap	Financial	DTM #2 (new IT), SH #2d	Non-LoB specific	TRL7 (deployment)
024	LINK	Green and climate Bonds investment	Financial	BM #4b	Non-LoB specific	TRL6 (development)
025	LINK	Resilience bonds	Financial	BM #4b	Non-LoB specific	TRL9 (development)
026	LINK	Insurance cover for mangroves	Financial	P&P #3b	Non-LoB specific	TRL7 (deployment)
027	LINK	Exchange of the best practices (ESG, innovative products, etc.)	Insurance business models	DTM #4	Non-LoB specific	TRL9 (deployment)

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028	LINK	Construction All Risk (CAR) policy for NBS	Insurance business models	P&P #3b, #3f	Infrastructure	TRL9 (deployment)
029	LINK	Green-building restauration	Insurance business models	BM #2d	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
030	NA, personal communication with reinsurers	Sales closing date-dependent Sliding Scale premiums	Insurance Marketing & Sales methods	P&P #2b	Agro	TRL1 (research)
031	LINK	Heat index insurance	Insurance Marketing & Sales methods	P&P #1a	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
032	LINK	Podcasts, blogs	Insurance Marketing & Sales methods	P&P #2d	Non-LoB specific	TRL5 (development)
033	LINK	Benchmarking, Evaluation of services	Insurance Marketing & Sales methods	P&P #2d	Non-LoB specific	TRL5 (development)
034	LINK	Income-dependent Sliding Scale premiums	Insurance Marketing & Sales methods	P&P #2b	Health	TRL9 (deployment)
035	NA, personal communication	Flood label	Insurance pricing methods and other policy terms (e.g., rates, deductibles, pay out limits)	BM #2c	House/ Building	TRL5 (development)
036	NA, personal communication with (re)insurers	Multi-year contracts offer affecting price	Insurance pricing methods and other policy terms (e.g., rates, deductibles, pay out limits)	P&P #2b	Non-LoB specific	TRL7 (deployment)
037	LINK	Affordable flood insurance designed specifically for homeowners in low-to-moderate risk areas	Insurance pricing methods and other policy terms (e.g., rates, deductibles, pay out limits)	DTM #1, #4	House/ Building	TRL4 (development)

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038	NA, personal communication	Criteria in the insurance contract rewarding CCA measures	Insurance pricing methods and other policy terms (e.g., rates, deductibles, pay out limits)	P&P #1b	House/ Building	TRL6 (development)
039	NA, personal communication	Risk-reduction conditions in the insurance contract (e.g. maintenance calendar) with small benefits	Insurance pricing methods and other policy terms (e.g., rates, deductibles, pay out limits)	BM #1a, #1b	House/ Building	TRL6 (development)
040	NA, personal communication	Regular house inspection	Insurance pricing methods and other policy terms (e.g., rates, deductibles, pay out limits)	BM #2c	House/ Building	TRL1 (research)
041	LINK 1 LINK 2	AVIVA flood-risk price differentiation, and USAA wildfire price differentiation	Insurance pricing methods and other policy terms (e.g., rates, deductibles, pay out limits)	P&P #1b, DTM #1, #3	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
042	LINK	New cover for NBS: sale of greenroofs	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3b	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
043	LINK 1 LINK 2 LINK 3	Block-chain based crop insurance	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	DTM #2 (new IT)	Non-LOB specific	TRL6 (development)
044	NA, personal communication	New cover for NBS: sale of NBS to private property owners and businesses	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3b	House/ Building	TRL4 (development)
045	LINK	Coverage for restoration to eco-label	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #1b	House/ Building	TRL1 (research)
046	LINK	Affordable insurance services	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #1b, BM #2d	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)

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047	LINK	PES (Payments for Environmental Services)-scheme	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3b	Non-LoB specific	TRL2 (research)
048	LINK	FLOW Insurance	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
049	LINK 1 LINK 2	HAIL Damage Insurance	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
050	LINK	Ecosystems interruption insurance product	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3b	Non-LOB specific	TRL3 (research)
051	LINK	Resilience Risk Transfer (RRT)	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	BM #4b, SH #2e	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
052	LINK	Weather risk insurance	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3d	Non-LOB	TRL9 (deployment)
053	LINK	Zurich Resilience Solutions	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
054	LINK	Transfer risks from atypical climate events	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3d, SH #2d, #2e	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
055	LINK	Mesoamerican reefs and communities protection	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3b	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
056	LINK 1 LINK 2	Eco-Rebuild Insurance Product	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #1b, BM #2d	Agro, House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
057	LINK	FORTIFIED Home Insurance Product	Insurance product types, e.g. new cover for NBS	P&P #3, BM #2	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)

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058	LINK	Agriculture Risk Metrics portal	Insurance services, e.g. supportive IT-solutions	BM #2a, DTM #4	Agro	TRL2 (research)
059	NA, personal communications	SaaS: On-line client & risk pooling service	Insurance services, e.g. supportive IT-solutions	BM #2a, DTM #1a, #4, P&P 3e	Non-LoB specific	TRL1 (research)
060	LINK	SMS extreme events alerts	Insurance services, e.g. supportive IT-solutions	BM #1a	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
061	NA, personal communication	SaaS: Visualization of CCA or NBS solutions risk-reduction potential	Insurance services, e.g. supportive IT-solutions	BM #2a, #2b, DTM #4	House/ Building	TRL5 (development)
062	NA, personal communication	Tool offered by insurer to city mayor to track public investment in buildings maintenance	Insurance services, e.g. supportive IT-solutions	BM #2a, #2b, DTM #4	House/ Building	TRL2 (research)
063	LINK	PPP for constructing green roofs, green areas, stormwater management system	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	SH #1a, BM #2d	House/ Building	TRL1 (research)
064	LINK	Parametric insurance solution	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	P&P #3d	House/ Building	TRL5 (development)
065	LINK	Insurer's pooling	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	SH #2c	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
066	LINK	State reinsurance	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	SH #2c	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
067	LINK	National Disaster Compensation Scheme	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	SH #2b	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)

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068	LINK	Natural Perils Pool /Natural Perils Insurance Scheme	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	SH #2b	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
069	LINK 1	Insurance Premium subsidies	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	SH #2a	House/ Building	TRL9 (deployment)
	LINK 2					
	LINK 3					
070	LINK	Discount Program to promote Best Practice in Agriculture (e.g. planting of cover crops).	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	SH #2a	Agro	TRL9 (deployment)
071	LINK	Technical assistance to SMEs	Public Private collaboration (beyond premium subsidy)	BM #2b	Infrastructure	TRL9 (deployment)
072	LINK	Non-linear heat index insurance	Risk quantification methods and models	P&P #3c, DTM #2	Agro	TRL1 (research)
073	LINK	ORSA and climate change scenarios	Risk quantification methods and models	DTM #3	Non-LOB specific	TRL9 (deployment)
074	LINK	Urban ESG reporting	Risk quantification methods and models	DTM #2, #3, #4	Non-LoB specific	TRL2 (research)
075	LINK	Aegis	Risk quantification methods and models	DTM #1b, #2, #3, #4	House/ Building	TRL7 (deployment)

*See Figure 16: Overview of different insurance solutions that can support climate change adaptation, grouped according to four pillars: Products & Pricing (P&P), Business Models (BM), Data, Technology and Models (DTM), and Shared Resilience (SH). Within each pillar, insurance solutions are numbered for reference.

**LOB: Line of Business.

***TRL: Technology Readiness Level.